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Parenting Style And Socio-Economic Status On Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviours Among Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the parenting style and socio-economic status on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses were answered and tested in the study, respectively. The descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized. The population of the study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2024/2025 academic year in Rivers State, with a total of one hundred and eighty-five thousand, two hundred and twenty-five (185,225) students. A 400 sample size was generated using the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. An adapted semi-structured closed-ended questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. To examine the evidence of the face and content validity, the instruments were validated by two experts. Split-half method was used for the reliability of the instrument. The analysis revealed a reliability index of 0.92 and 0.91 for parenting style and socio-economic status data; prevalence of heterosexual behaviour was 0.79. The data was computed and analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive and inferential (chi-square) statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the proxies of the independent variable. The findings on which adolescents engage in sexual intercourse are of significant public health importance, as it has been found to expose them to potential risky outcomes both in the short and long term. It can be concluded that the existence of sufficient information does not guarantee avoidance of sexual behaviour. The study concluded that there is a positive and low significant relationship between parenting style and socio-economic status on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Consequently, it was recommended among others that parents and school teachers should be empowered through capacity building on sexuality education so that they can teach/educate the children/students on sexual and reproductive health. This will prevent adolescents from seeking such information from their peers.

Keywords: parenting style, socio-economic status, adolescent, heterosexual, behaviours, senior secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, the heterosexual behaviour of adolescents has been a significant topic of research, particularly in light of the emerging Covid-19 pandemic. According to Omorodion et al. (2021) and Kar et al. (2015), adolescents' heterosexual behaviour has increasingly become the subject of moral and policy discussions, with anal and oral sex becoming prevalent practices, and these behaviours tend to rise with age. This trend is noteworthy because adolescents represent a vital demographic

within any society, and their health and sexual behaviours can impact the future health and norms of the community. In Nigeria, the adolescent population, defined as individuals aged 10 to 24 years, makes up approximately 31.4 per cent of the total population. Adolescents are not a uniform group; their needs differ widely based on factors such as age, gender, region, socioeconomic status, and cultural background. Likewise, their sexual and reproductive health requirements vary significantly across different cultures, groups, and religions. This variability is influenced by the physiological and psychological changes that incite a desire for sexual activity and risk-taking. This stage of life is sensitive and presents unique challenges, particularly concerning sexual and reproductive health, due to the developmental transformations they undergo.

While adolescents are biologically capable of reproduction, engaging in sexual behaviour at this age can lead to various long-term negative outcomes. Furthermore, when adolescent girls participate in risky sexual activities, they become more vulnerable to reproductive health issues, potentially leading to teenage pregnancies that necessitate complex decisions, such as opting to become teen parents or seeking to terminate the pregnancy. This challenge stems from the difficulty adolescent girls often face in discussing sexuality openly, which results in them relying on information primarily from boys. Additionally, the tendency of adolescents to engage in risky sexual behaviour increases their chances of contracting sexually transmitted infections, including HIV/AIDS. If adolescents fail to pursue prompt treatment for sexually transmitted infections, they may encounter long-term health complications. In addition to health risks, adolescent sexual behaviour can disrupt academic performance; a perspective supported by Lanari et al. (2020), who found a correlation between sexual activity and reduced participation in educational activities. The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) (2019) reported that among all new HIV cases in adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa, 80% occur in girls aged 15 to 19 years. Furthermore, adolescent girls and young women are twice as likely to be living with HIV compared to their male counterparts of the same age, regardless of their reports indicating having only one sexual partner and infrequent sexual encounters.

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines adolescents as individuals aged 10 to 19 years, a demographic that exhibits varying proportions across both developed and developing countries (WHO, 2019). The transitional period between childhood and adulthood is referred to as adolescence, a crucial stage characterised by significant biological, psychological, and social changes. In Nigeria, a country with one of the largest youth populations globally, approximately one in four individuals falls within this adolescent age bracket, making it home to over 36 million adolescents aged 10 to 19 years (Nigeria Demographic Health Survey, 2018; World Population Review, 2015).

Despite being a vital segment of the population, adolescents in Nigeria face a myriad of challenges related to sexual and reproductive health. These issues often stem from socio-cultural factors, limited access to health education, and inadequate healthcare services (United Nations Children's Fund, 2020). According to Brizio et al. (2015), an adolescent is neither a child nor yet an adult; this age group is marked by a range of developmental changes including physical growth, emotional maturation, and significant shifts in social relationships. The onset of adolescence is typically aligned with the beginning of puberty, yet the developmental timeline can vary significantly among individuals. Adolescents often experience non-linear growth patterns, evident through sudden physical changes and fluctuating emotional maturity. While adolescents constitute about 21 per cent of the population in developed countries, they represent a higher percentage—around 29 per cent—in developing nations like Nigeria. Recent statistics indicate that there are over 1.5 billion individuals aged 10 to 24 worldwide, the largest such demographic in history, with 85 per cent residing in developing regions (WHO 2019). This demographic surge has prompted researchers and policymakers in these areas to focus intensively on adolescent reproductive health, aiming to address and mitigate adverse social and health behaviours that have become deeply entrenched in society (United Nations Children Fund, 2020).

Adolescence is marked by transformative changes in preferences, experiences, desires, behaviour, and sexuality. As young people navigate this pivotal stage in life, they are often exposed to modern influences—most notably the internet—which shapes their perspectives on sexuality and relationships. The interplay of these factors profoundly affects the decision-making processes and overall health outcomes of adolescents. This period of transition brings new challenges including the initiation of sexual activity, engagement in risk-taking behaviours, and decisions regarding intimate

relationships and family formation, all of which can significantly impact future health and social opportunities (United Nations, 2012).

Investing in critical areas such as health (particularly sexual and reproductive health), education, and economic opportunities is essential to ensure that adolescents can maximise their potential and develop their human capital effectively. Adolescents have unique health and developmental needs, and the age at which they engage in sexual activities carries significant public health implications. Research indicates that individuals who begin sexual activity at younger ages are more likely to engage in risky sexual behaviours, such as having casual partners and multiple concurrent relationships (WHO, 2014; Uchudi et al., 2012). Addressing these issues through comprehensive education and healthcare strategies is vital for fostering healthier behaviours among adolescents and improving their long-term outcomes.

Forms of Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviour

Sexual behaviour encompasses a wide range of activities beyond just sexual intercourse, including actions such as holding hands, kissing, and fondling. As adolescents navigate their romantic relationships, they invest significant time in thinking about, discussing, and participating in these connections. The quality of adolescent romantic relationships can have lasting impacts on self-esteem and shape personal values related to romance, intimacy, and sexuality (Mapalad & Psych, 2014). Statistics indicate that about one in three 13-year-olds has experienced a romantic relationship, with this number increasing as they age. By age 17, a majority have had some involvement in such relationships, typically engaging in around four different partnerships during their teenage years. Cultural influences also play a crucial role in determining the timing and frequency of these relationships. For instance, Asian American teenagers often enter romantic relationships later compared to their peers, as dating is generally less accepted within many Asian cultures.

Sexual minority youth encounter additional barriers in finding potential partners. While many adolescents typically meet romantic interests at school, sexual minority youth may struggle to find inclusive social circles, exacerbated by discrimination and a lower number of openly out peers. Perceived social norms significantly affect the quality of adolescent relationships as well. Research shows that boys who believe aggression is common among their peers are more likely to exhibit aggressive behaviours in their romantic relationships. Additionally, friendships with sexually experienced or older peers can lead to earlier sexual activity, as the desire for approval or fear of disapproval from peers often influences sexual decision-making.

To minimise the risks associated with adolescent romantic relationships, it is essential to equip young people with skills that foster healthy connections. Sexually active adolescents in supportive relationships tend to practice safer behaviours, including consistent contraceptive use, open discussions about sexual history, and sexual exclusivity (Weitzman et al., 2019).

Moreover, school and community programs designed to address gender-based stereotypes, enhance conflict management and communication skills, and reduce tolerance for partner violence have proven effective in decreasing dating violence among adolescents (Foshee et al., 2011).

Parenting Style

Parents play a critical role in instilling positive sexual values in adolescents. While families are a vital part of the social environment in which young people live, learn, and grow, they can significantly contribute to the healthy development of adolescents (Wang et al., 2007). However, the challenge of parenting during adolescence lies in offering opportunities for young people to cultivate and practice their autonomy while also protecting them from dangers and the potential consequences of poor decisions regarding sexual relationships. Researchers are particularly interested in identifying parental factors that predict adolescents' sexual behaviour. Parenting styles are generally characterised by levels of warmth and control, leading to four key styles:

1. Authoritarian parents: strict control without support
2. Permissive/indulgent parents: high support with little control
3. Neglectful/uninvolved parents: neither supportive nor controlling
4. Authoritative parents: high support with strict control

Studies have focused on how parenting practices relate to adolescent sexual behaviour, examining crucial constructs such as parental monitoring and communication between parents and children (Steinberg, 2001). Research suggests that a reciprocal relationship between parents and adolescents enhances adolescents' security, their ability to respond appropriately to stress, and their receptiveness

to various parenting practices aimed at fostering healthy socialisation (Liable & Thompson, 2008). Evidence indicates that open conversations with parents about sexuality and reproductive health—characterised by warmth, support, and humour—are linked to a later onset of sexual activity and reduced sexual risk-taking (Trejos-Castillo & Vazsonyi, 2009).

According to Ncheta (2011), parenting style refers to how parents raise their children, which can depend on their expectations, performance levels, attentiveness to rules, and disciplinary methods. Numerous research efforts have explored the relationship between parenting style and adolescent sexual behaviour. However, some studies suggest that parental monitoring may have a limited impact on adolescents' sexual behaviour. For example, Dittus et al. (2015) found a consistent pattern of sexual risk behaviours among adolescents who perceived low levels of parental monitoring. While parents exert considerable influence on behaviour, adolescents' sexual practices often contradict societal ethics and values. Research indicates that parenting styles have both direct and indirect effects on children's outcomes. Adolescents of authoritative parents—who maintain positive relationships, healthy communication, and perceived support—are less likely to engage in sexual risk behaviours (Ishak et al., 2012). Additionally, low levels of perceived parental warmth and knowledge have been linked to earlier sexual onset (Rodgers & McGuire, 2012).

Nevertheless, there is a lack of studies testing the contextual model of parenting style. Few have examined the relationship between parental practices and child outcomes specifically within this framework. Existing studies indicate that this relationship is strongest among children of authoritative parents (Shehu & Kryeziu, 2015; Hancock-Hoskins, 2014). Unfortunately, these studies have not adequately addressed the mechanisms through which parenting styles influence adolescent sexual behaviours.

Socio-economic Status of Parent/Guardian

Attitudes towards sexuality in adolescents are shaped by their experiences and various social contexts. The concept of sexuality is multidimensional, encompassing not only biological and psychological aspects but also cultural, social, and historical factors that influence the individual. It plays a crucial role in personality development, the learning process, and the physical and mental health of adolescents. Additionally, sexuality is linked to personal values and desires and is a significant element in the formation of identity. In Nigeria, adolescent sexual health presents ongoing challenges for health policies, addressing not just biological concerns, but also psychosocial issues (Sasaki et al., 2014).

Socioeconomic status (SES), often measured by family income or educational attainment, is associated with various health indicators, including adult and child mortality rates and reproductive health outcomes like unintended pregnancies, adolescent birth rates, and infant mortality. Risky behaviours during the teenage years often vary by socioeconomic status. Many adult health behaviours also differ according to SES, with lower socioeconomic status correlating with a higher prevalence of unhealthy behaviours. Factors such as family size, income, housing type, living environment, social values, and job nature can all influence adolescents' sexual behaviour. A study conducted in Ibadan found that poverty, lack of parental supervision, and parents working long hours contribute to adolescents—especially those out of school—engaging in unnecessary sexual relationships.

Baker et al. (2015) explored the relationship between theism, secularism, and sexual education in the United States. The purpose of the study was to determine how the religious composition of a state's population affects its sexual health education policies. Data for the study was gathered from several sources, including the Pew Religious Landscape Survey, the Religious Congregations and Membership Study, and interviews with politicians. The Pew Religious Landscape Survey focused on scriptural literalism, service attendance, and levels of theism, with a sample size of 35,957. The Religious Congregations and Membership Study, with a sample size of 3,142, was used to assess religious adherence and evangelical adherence. Additionally, 400 politicians were interviewed regarding their political alliances. The findings indicated that states with high levels of self-reported theism are more likely to have sexual health education that emphasises abstinence-only programs. In contrast, states with low levels of theism are more likely to have sexual health education that includes contraceptive information. The study suggested that policy changes in states with abstinence-only education may be more successful if approached through a public health model rather than a separation of church and state model.

Udigwe et al. (2014) examined the factors influencing sexual behaviour among female adolescents in Onitsha, Nigeria. The study utilised a cross-sectional design, selecting a total of 800 female adolescents from secondary schools in the area using a multistage sampling method. Additionally, participants were selected from a major market for those who were not in school, using a cluster sampling technique. The highest proportion of students who reported having ever had sex was found among the 16- to 17-year age group, while the modal age for non-students was 18 to 19 years. Factors such as “not living with both parents” and a poor family background were significantly associated with an increased likelihood of engaging in sexual activity. Additionally, poverty levels were notably high among non-student adolescents. The study also found that misconceptions about fertile periods, low risk perception of HIV, and limited condom use were all significantly related to an increased likelihood of sexual engagement. Student adolescents primarily received sexuality information from teachers, whereas non-student counterparts relied more on youth organisations and peers.

Ugoji (2014) studied the determinants of risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. Using a survey design, the study investigated how emotional intelligence, self-esteem, religiosity, and media influence risky sexual behaviour among 300 secondary school students from 10 schools within Asaba metropolis. Five instruments were administered to the participants, and data were analysed with descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The results indicated significant relationships between risky sexual behaviour and the independent variables; however, the relationships between risky sexual behaviour and both emotional intelligence and religiosity were negatively significant. The independent variables accounted for approximately 43% of the variation in risky sexual behaviour among adolescents, with religiosity being the most influential factor. The study recommended incorporating emotional intelligence and self-esteem training into the school curriculum and encouraging participation in religious activities to enhance the moral development of adolescents.

Rumun (2014) investigated the role of religion in the reproductive health behaviour of youths in Makurdi, Benue State. Data were collected from a representative sample of youths residing in the Makurdi local government area, with a total of 550 youths sampled using a purposive sampling technique. The results were presented in frequencies and percentages, and the relationship between religious commitment and youth reproductive behaviour was assessed. The study found that religion appeared to be irrelevant for youths, as many engaged in sexual intercourse before marriage despite being aware of religious values. It also revealed that peers and mass media had a greater influence on sexual attitudes and behaviours than religion did. While religious practices are expected to affect youth reproductive health behaviour and attitudes toward premarital sexual activity, this was not evident in the practical lives of the youths. Given that religion does not significantly influence adolescents' sexual lifestyles, the study urged religious representatives to acknowledge this disconnect and assist the state in supporting HIV/AIDS and STI prevention initiatives, as well as formulating accurate health policies in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescents in Nigeria are often expected to adhere to traditional values, such as maintaining chastity until marriage, refraining from late-night outings, and closely following their parents' guidance to mitigate the risks associated with unhealthy sexual behaviours. Despite these expectations, a significant number of adolescents engage in sexual activities. The National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA) reports that approximately 1.9 million adults and 130,000 children under the age of 15 are living with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria, underscoring an urgent need for targeted educational and health programs aimed at this age group. Research indicates that many HIV infections occur during adolescence, with the virus sometimes remaining dormant for up to a decade, making early intervention critical.

In Rivers State, Nigeria, there has been a concerning rise in unplanned pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among adolescents, pointing to a dire need for improved sexual health education, access to contraceptives, and reliable guidance. The prevalence of early sexual initiation and engagement in risky behaviours is alarmingly high, exacerbated by limited access to comprehensive sexual education and the socio-cultural barriers that inhibit open discussions about sexual health. Government initiatives aimed at youth empowerment and sexual health education are currently insufficient, and prevalent cultural norms often stigmatise discussions about sexual health, further complicating the situation. Many young girls face significant consequences, such as dropping

out of school due to pregnancies or becoming affected by HIV/AIDS, which can drastically alter their life paths.

Despite clear evidence of increased risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in Rivers State, there remains a notable gap in empirical research addressing this issue within sub-Saharan Africa. Most existing studies primarily focus on the western regions of Nigeria, leaving a void in data specific to Rivers State. Consequently, this research aims to thoroughly investigate the prevalence and determinants of heterosexual behaviour among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State, to inform effective intervention strategies. Such research will provide valuable insights that can help shape policies and programs to safeguard the health and well-being of adolescents in the region.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the parenting style and socio-economic status on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Investigate the influence of parenting style on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
- ii. Assess the influence of socio-economic status of parent/guardian on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. To what extent does parenting style influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
- ii. To what extent does socio-economic status of parent/guardian influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

- i. There is no significant relationship between parenting style and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between socio-economic status of parent/guardian and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized to achieve the purpose of this study. The population of the study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2022/2023 academic year in Rivers State with a total of one hundred and eighty-five thousand, two hundred and twenty-five (185,225) students. From the total population of 185,225 students, 400 sample size was generated using the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. Thereafter, the sample size for the study was multiplied by three, representing the three senatorial districts. One thousand two hundred (1200) students were randomly selected from twelve (12) LGAs across the three (3) Senatorial Districts. For the composition of respondents, a non-proportionate stratified random sampling technique was utilised to sample equal (100) respondents from each of the sampled schools, thereby arriving at 1200 respondents, which was used for the study. An adapted semi-structured closed-ended questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The data for this study were collected through the administration of a pre-designed, re-tested, semi-structured questionnaire to respondents. To ensure the validity of the research instrument (the questionnaire), there was an extensive literature review relating to the topic. Furthermore, to examine the evidence of the face and content validity, the instruments were validated by two experts. Split-half method was used for the reliability of the instrument. Fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were administered to 50 students at the same time. Later, the questionnaires were numbered from 1 to 50. The even numbers were made to be group one (1) while odd numbers were made to be group two (2). Thereafter, the two groups of data were analyzed using Kuder Richardson version 20 (Dichotomous options). The analysis revealed a reliability index of 0.94 for socio-demographic data, and prevalence of heterosexual behaviour was 0.78. The researcher employed three research assistants to assist in administering the questionnaires to the students in the selected schools. The items on the instrument were read out to them, and the respondents followed the instructions in completing the questionnaire. The data collection exercise lasted for four (4) months. The data analysis method for the study was descriptive statistical analyses.

The data was computed and analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel, Univariate (frequency and simple percentage) were used to analyze demographic variables while descriptive and inferential (chi-square) statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the proxies of the independent variable (peer pressure and religious affiliation) on the dependent variable (adolescent heterosexual behaviour).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does parenting influence adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Parenting as a determinant of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours

S.N		Frequency	Percent
1	I have received sex education from my parents.		
	No	1008	84.0
	Yes	192	16.0
2	I can freely ask my parents questions about sexuality.		
	No	912	76.0
	Yes	288	24.0
3	My parents usually encourage me to express my feelings positively.		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
4	My parents have few or no expectations or demands for behaviour.		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
5	My parents encourage and teach me what I do not know.		
	No	384	32.0
	Yes	816	68.0
6	My parents offer little or no supervision for what I do.		
	No	576	48.0
	Yes	624	52.0
Average			
	No	576	48
	Yes	624	52

Source: Field survey (2023): Key: 0-25% = Low; 26-50% = Moderate; 51-100% = High

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of parenting as a determinant of adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings reveal that only 192(16%) of students reported having received sex education from my parents. 24% of the respondents indicated that they can freely ask their parents questions about sexuality. However, 76% of the respondents indicated that they receive encouragement from their parents for their feelings and that their parents have few or no expectations on demands for their behaviour. On the other hand, 68% of the respondents indicated that their parents encourage and teach them what they do not know and offer little or no supervision for what they do. According to these findings, adolescents engaged in sexual behaviours due to low monitoring. The fact that few students reported having engaged in sexual intercourse may mean that parental monitoring served as a protective factor. This is in agreement that rule setting, supervision, and authoritative values transmitted to adolescents determine the age and frequency of involvement in adolescent sex initiation.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does socioeconomic status of parent/guardian influence adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Socioeconomic status of parent/guardian as a determinant of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours

		Monthly Family Income (₦)			
		Less than 30,000	30,000-4999	50,000 & above	I don't know
1	Have you ever held hands with the opposite sex?				
	No	24	72	96	0
	Yes	168	504	240	96
2	Have you ever practised kissing with the opposite sex?				
	No	91	257	56	36
	Yes	101	319	280	60
3	Have you ever had sexual intercourse?				
	No	73	189	137	56
	Yes	119	387	199	40
4	Have you ever engaged in oral sex?				
	No	72	192	24	0
	Yes	120	384	312	96
5	Have you ever engaged in anal sex?				
	No	72	219	97	0
	Yes	120	357	239	96
6	Have you ever engaged in masturbation?				
	No	72	240	241	24
	Yes	120	336	95	72
7	Have you ever engaged in blow-job?				
	No	120	312	170	72
	Yes	72	264	166	24
8	Have you ever engaged in fingering?				
	No	96	312	241	24
	Yes	96	264	95	72
9	Have you ever engaged in fingering?				
	No	120	409	264	0
	Yes	72	167	72	96
10	Have you ever engaged in fellatio?				
	No	120	336	312	96
	Yes	72	240	24	0
11	Have you ever experienced dry humping or genital rubbing?				
	No	57	143	111	30
	Yes	135	433	225	66
Average					
	No	83 (7%)	244 (20%)	159 (13%)	31 (3%)
	Yes	109 (9%)	332 (28%)	177 (15%)	65 (5%)

Source: *Field survey (2023)*

Table 2 displays the frequency percentage distribution of social economic status (SES) of parent/guardian influences adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The results revealed that adolescents across all economic statuses engaged in all the sexual behaviours studied. However, it was notable that the percentages of adolescents engaging in the various behaviours were negligible as revealed by 28% from SES of NGN30,000-

49,999, 15% from SES of NGN50,000 and above, 9% from SES of less than NGN30,000, and 5% from respondents who have no idea about their parents' socio-economic status. Adolescents who reported having engaged in heterosexual behaviours were highest in SES of NGN30,000-49,999 and lowest among adolescents that have no idea about their parents' socio-economic status. These findings indicate that adolescents who reported having engaged in the various sexual behaviours across parental socioeconomic brackets investigated were much as revealed by those high percentages reported for sex behaviour and socioeconomic category. However, students from SES of NGN30,000-49,999 show slightly higher percentages in the sexual behaviours reported. This can be explained by the assumptions that adolescents from the low-income brackets may engage in sex as one of the ways to get money and other valuables.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parenting style and adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 3: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between parenting and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Parenting	No	F	244	332	X ₂ (1)=2.021 P>.155
		%	20.3%	27.7%	
	Yes	F	276	348	
		%	23.0%	29.0%	

Table 3 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between parenting and adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study revealed a non-significant relationship between parenting and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours (X₂=2.021, df=1, p>05). Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between parenting and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State, was retained.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Family Monthly Income	Less than 30,000	F	1	5	X ₂ (3)=0.915 P>.822
		%	1%	5%	
	30,000-49,999	F	1	5	
		%	9%	1%	
	50,000 and above	F	1	5	
		%	7%	3%	
	I don't know	F	1	5	
		%	1%	5%	

Table 4 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study revealed a non-significant relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours (X₂=0.915, df=1, p>05). Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State, was retained.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

According to the first findings, adolescents engaged in sexual behaviours due to low monitoring. The fact that few students reported having engaged in sexual intercourse may mean that parental monitoring served as a protective factor. This is in agreement that rule setting, supervision, and

authoritative values transmitted to adolescents determine the age and frequency of involvement in adolescent sex initiation. Also, there is no significant relationship between parenting and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. In line with the findings are Akumiah et al. (2020); Adongo (2019); Durowade et al. (2017); World Health Organisation (2020). They posit that studies in other contexts have equally identified that adolescents were engaging in sexual activities even before their 13th birthday. This suggests that adolescents start having sexual relationships as early as 11 years, and therefore, parents, guardians, and health workers should start reproductive health education as early as possible, aimed at empowering children even before they turn 11 years. This also contributes to increasing teenage pregnancies, especially in Africa where about 14 million teenage pregnancies occur each year. It has also been estimated in sub-Saharan Africa that between 10% and 79% of all pregnancies in women below 20 years of age are described as unwanted. This suggests the need for youth empowerment on issues of reproductive health.

These findings indicate that adolescents who reported having engaged in the various sexual behaviours across parental socioeconomic brackets investigated were much as revealed by the high percentages reported for sex behaviour and socioeconomic category. However, students from SES of NGN30,000-49,999 show slightly higher percentages in the sexual behaviours reported. This can be explained by the assumptions that adolescents from the low-income brackets may engage in sex as one of the ways to get money and other valuables. Also, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status of parent/guardian and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State, was retained. In agreement with these sentiments Kirby, Coyle, Alton, Roller and Robin (2011) economic opportunities and family factors such as a strong family are factors determining adolescent sexuality while (Kirby, Laris & Roller, 2001; Luke, 2003; Didi, 2004; UNICEF, 2006 suggested that economic deprivation is a risk factor for sexual initiation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the comprehensive findings and in-depth discussions presented in the study, it was concluded that there is a positive and low significant relationship between parenting style and socio-economic status on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Parents and school teachers should be empowered through capacity building on sexuality education so that they can teach/educate the children/students on sexual and reproductive health. This will prevent adolescents from seeking such information from their peers.
2. Policy makers and curriculum planners should advocate for inclusion of sexuality education in basic and secondary school curriculum as a matter of priority to foster a positive attitude, knowledge, and behaviour of the adolescents towards sexuality..

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